

HALAL ECONOMIC: CHALLENGES AND EMERGING OPPORTUNITIES IN MALAYSIA

Wan Shahzlinda Shah Shahar^{a*}; Nadzirah Mohd Fauzi^b; Mohd Fadhli Ab Rahman^c;

Nur Iman Hashim^d and Wan Suraya Wan Hassin.^e

^{a)} *Department of Accounting and Finance, Faculty of Management and Muamalah,
Kolej Universiti Islam Antarabangsa Selangor, Malaysia. Email: wanshahzlinda@kuis.edu.my*

^{b)} *Department of Economic and Management, Faculty of Management and Muamalah,
Kolej Universiti Islam Antarabangsa Selangor, Malaysia. Email: nadzirah@kuis.edu.my*

^{c)} *Department of Economic and Management, Faculty of Management and Muamalah,
Kolej Universiti Islam Antarabangsa Selangor, Malaysia. Email: mohdfadhli@kuis.edu.my*

^{d)} *School of Hospitality and Tourism,
SEGi University, Malaysia. Email: nurimanhashim@segi.edu.my*

^{e)} *Department of Accounting and Finance, Faculty of Management and Muamalah,
Kolej Universiti Islam Antarabangsa Selangor, Malaysia. Email: wansuraya@kuis.edu.my*

Abstract

The global Halal market has emerged in the global economy and forming a strong presence in developed countries. Halal transcends the traditional industry-sector boundaries, geographic, cultural, and even religious boundaries. The market for certified Halal products is developing robustly, both domestically and internationally. In this industry, Malaysia has become the leader and center of reference for the world. Malaysia consistently have undertaken the significant initiatives across regulation, trade and industry support to strengthen the status as hubs in the trade-driven Islamic economy. Halal industry expanding fast and becoming the new market paradigm with its own unique set of challenges and opportunities. Therefore, this study tend to explore on the challenges and emerging opportunities of halal industry in Malaysia.

Keywords: Halal industry, challenges, opportunities and Islamic economic.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Halal transcends the traditional industry-sector boundaries, geographic, cultural, and even religious boundaries. From a business perspective, the halal market undoubtedly offers a range of compelling opportunities. As many traditional markets reach saturation, the emergence of a new market, based on halal values and principles, is in effect creating a new commercial paradigm. This is strongly led by the food and beverage sector, and has more recently expanded into the pharmaceutical, cosmetic and personal-care sectors, driven by increasing consumer awareness and an entrepreneurial eye for new market opportunities. Thus, this industry is competing and struggling to capture the unique consumer segment with the values, ethics and trust as Malaysia is the key mover of halal industry (Mahathir, 2010).

Since Halal is a 'farm-to-fork' process and all the way through the supply chain, aspects such as warehousing, transportation and logistics all play a role in maintaining and demonstrating Halal integrity. Consumers nowadays become more concerned towards halal (Lada, 2010) matters and they expect the final product is safe to be consume (Kim and Chung, 2011). The Halal market is a complex and fragmented jigsaw puzzle whose defining parameters are still fluid and expanding. Variables based on cultural assumptions, habits and preferences, different interpretations of the law and the global nature of food product supply chains add to this complexity. From consumer awareness to technological innovations, the Halal market is continuously being influenced and driven to new levels of evolution.

In line with this development, the Malaysian Government is focusing on increasing halal products in making Malaysia an international halal hub. Thus, one of the best achievement is when Malaysian Halal Certification, which is designed to cater the halal goods sectors, have been named as the world's best example for halal food benchmarking by the United Nation in 1997 (Bohari, Wei Hin & Fuad, 2013). The halal companies, especially those in food processing, can depend on Malaysia's strength in halal certification, as Malaysia was the

pioneer in establishing halal laws in the early 1980s and remains a force in matters relating to halal certification globally. In addition, Malaysia is positioning itself as the knowledge center for the trade and investment promotion of halal products and services by organizing the Malaysia International Halal Showcase (MIHAS) and the World Halal Forum (WHF), as the international avenue for showcasing the halal trade (MATRADE 2011).

2.0 THE HALAL ECONOMY AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF HALAL INDUSTRY IN MALAYSIA

Halal economy is new terms used recently as a new agenda that will be future of global economic and social. It is reflect both separated system of halal product and Islamic finance to be integrated and become the new model of economy (Ahmad (2008), Abdalhamid Evans (2011), Irfan Ishak & Che Man (2011), Siddiqui (2013), Irfan Ishak, M. Daud, & Suhaimi (2014) and MIFC (2014). It means, the Islamic finance and Halal industries are inter-related and a perfect symbiosis nexus (Norafni & Zurina, 2016). In the other words, the capital from Asian Social Science Vol. 10, it state that Islamic banking and finance industry should be channeled to Halal industry to ensure the comprehensiveness of the compliance. The financial assistance in further could be interpreted in the variety forms of financial instruments including the equity, sukuk and Islamic banking products.

Due to high demand from Muslim consumers around the world, the market for certified Halal products is growing robustly, both domestically and internationally. This statement have been supported by the previous research from Fleishman (2012), it state that the global Muslim population is expected to grow by about 35 percent over the next 20 years, rising from 1.6 billion in 2010 to 2.2 billion by 2030, or 26.4 percent of the world's total projected population of 8.3 billion. By 2050, the Muslim population could grow to 2.6 billion and represent nearly 30 percent of the global projected population. Also by 2030, 79 countries are expected to hold

a million or more Muslim residents, as opposed to the current 72 countries. Thus, in order to be successful in Asia, Middle East and North Africa, business player must learn to understand and address the Muslim market on a large scale.

Figure 1: The World Muslim Population

In Malaysia, a more holistic approach towards the development of a Halal industry and creating a Halal ecosystem is being undertaken by the government with the principal aim of positioning Malaysia as a global Halal hub by 2020 (Yuhanis & Chok 2012). Today, Malaysia is a leader in the Halal food benchmarking. The United Nations has cited Malaysia as the world's best example of benchmarking of Halal food in accordance with the Codex Alimentarius Commission adopted the Codex general guidelines for the use of the term Halal in Geneva in 1997. This is because a single Halal standard is applied throughout the country with the result that the Malaysian standard has become the basis for the development of the world's Halal food industries (SME Annual Report 2006, 2007).

Figure 2: Top 10 of Global Islamic Economy Indicator Score.

Tapping into this vast opportunity, Malaysia needs to strengthen the Halal institutions or government agencies in order to capture the goals in becoming the global Halal Hub. Malaysia has a few institutions or government agencies together with non-government organization, NGOs (Muslim Consumer Group (MSG) and Halal center in several public universities) established in order to focus on Halal standard development, Halal training, Halal research and development (R&D), Halal innovation, Halal logistics, Halal port services and Islamic financial services, Halal production and manufacturing of Halal product and services. The establishment Halal Development Corporation (HDC), to work closely with Department of Islamic Development Malaysia (JAKIM), has further boosted the progression of Halal development in Malaysia.

JAKIM is particularly vital as it holds the sole responsibility for issuing halal certification. In addition, HDC provides the necessary infrastructure to facilitate investment in the Malaysian halal industry (HDC 2012). The establishment of halal parks by the HDC is among the measures introduced to facilitate the growth of the industry. The establishment of halal parks is a key step towards improving the downstream production of halal products, and to provide manufacturers, both local and foreign, with the means to establish and maintain internationally accepted manufacturing process standards that incorporate both the scientific

and religious requirements for ensuring halal integrity. At this stage, the HDC has established nine halal parks; nine are under development and two are planned to be built in the near future. At present, there are 28 companies operating in this halal park, which is expected to further increase in the future.

In addition, there are various supporting services established by the Malaysian Government to ensure the smooth running of the halal industry, ranging from the processing procedure to promotion and transportation. Besides the government initiatives, there is also support provided by Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), such as the Muslim Consumer Group (MSG), at both the national and state level, and the halal centers in several universities in Malaysia. The halal industry should cover all aspects of producing halal products (particularly halal food), such as transportation, packaging, labelling and logistics of the products (Mukhtar & Butt, 2012). There are ongoing efforts in creating Malaysia as the halal hub. Addressing this integrative approach and the continuous efforts of various halal agencies and institutions, has contributed to the positive demand for halal products from RM50 million in 2005 to RM260 million in 2010 (HDC, 2012).

3.0 SEGMENTATIONS OF THE HALAL MARKET

The realm of halal not only refer to food but may extend to other final products such as toiletries, pharmaceuticals and nutraceutical, cosmetics and services including tourism and finance. The concept of halal was taken for granted previously, as nations were generally self-sufficient in food production. With the onslaught of global trade and changing lifestyles, non-Muslim countries are dominating the trade of processed food and generally halal products. Currently, a certain degree of assurance is provided by halal certification of halal products, which in any case can be issued by any of over 100 halal certification bodies worldwide (The Halal Journal, 2008). Each organization has their own set of halal standards and guidelines.

The fragmentation is further accentuated when crossing national boundaries where to date there is no functioning mechanism for mutual recognition between countries. The lack of proper regulation of certification means that non-halal produce has unknowingly ended up on the plates of Muslim households (IslamOnline.net, 2006).

Figure 4: Segments of the Halal Market

3.1 HALAL FOOD SEGMENTATION

Driven by growing demand, the Halal food market continues to build its momentum across the global food supply chain. The State of the Global Islamic Economy (SGIE) 2018/2019 estimates that Muslim spend on food and beverage was valued at USD1.3 trillion in 2017, and growing at 6.1% forecast to reach USD1.9 trillion by 2023. The top 5 world leading Islamic economy ecosystem for Halal food based on Global Islamic Economy (GIE) Indicator are UAE, Malaysia, Brazil, Oman and Jordan. Based on total Muslim food expenditure, the top 5 countries are Indonesia, Turkey, Pakistan, Egypt and Bangladesh. The Halal food trade opportunity is attractive, but much movement in the leader board of exporters is anticipated, with China, Philippines and Canada all making important moves.

Figure 3: Top 15 of State of Islamic Economic Report Indicator Score (2016)

Numerous product categories are ripe for exploration in the Halal food industry, notably organic products. Organic food is gaining substantial traction in Saudi Arabia, with 33% of consumers purchasing more organic products over the last 12 months, which bodes well for Halal organic food producers, such as Saffron Roads. There is a Halal mozzarella boom in Italy, with annual production reaching over 10 million kilos by end of 2016, and with one in 10 mozzarellas destined for OIC countries, the UAE is a top destination. There is substantial opportunity for Halal sweets, as evidenced by Haribo's opening a Halal sweet shop in the UK.

China is staking its claim in the international Halal food trade opportunity, investing AED1.35 billion in the Dubai Food Park, a specialized food industrial cluster. Two leading poultry producers in Canada, Sargent Farms of Ontario and Boire & Frères Inc. of Quebec, have invested USD10 million to enhance their Halal processing capabilities. Kyrgyzstan has sought to participate in the Halal food export opportunity, as a first step, introducing voluntary Halal certification program for local producers. The Philippines is seeking to gain a substantial share of the Halal export opportunity, after the Development Promotion Board accepted the requirements of the Halal Export and Development Act 2016, and with the local development of the Asian Halal Center, a 100-hectare Halal processing facility to house producers.

Malaysia and the UAE, seek to cement their central role in the Halal food industry, and are beginning to work together to set up a Halal corridor. Malaysia has sought to allocate RM1 billion for a Halal Development Fund. Malaysia is extending its Halal certification services to China to oversee local companies, Xinjiang, Gansu, Xian and Lanzhou, where 5,000 companies are said to be producing Halal. The UAE has for the first time quantified the size and scale of its Halal economy, estimating the Islamic economy at 8.3% of GDP. Malaysia has officially recognized the UAE's Halal Product Control System which comprises the national certificates, Halal logos and facilitating the export of products into Malaysia, as well as the 60 countries that accept Malaysia's certification system. Halal food is an attractive prospect for investors, but still remains a challenging.

3.2 PHARMACEUTICAL, NUTRACEUTICAL AND HEALTH PRODUCTS

Pharmaceutical and health products are also large growth areas in the global Halal industry. The State of the Global Islamic Economy (SGIE) 2018/2019 estimates that Muslim spend on pharmaceutical was valued at USD 87 billion in 2017, and growing at 7.1% forecast to reach USD131 billion by 2023. The top 5 world leading Islamic economy ecosystem for Halal pharmaceutical and cosmetics based on Global Islamic Economy (GIE) Indicator are UAE, Malaysia, Singapore, Jordan and Pakistan. Based on total Muslim pharmaceutical expenditure, the top 5 countries are Turkey, Saudi Arabia, United States, Indonesia and Algeria. The main concern among Muslims is the use of non-compliant substances such as animal derivatives and animal-based gelatins in these products. The rising healthcare costs also provide the Halal market with a key differentiation factor in the supply of generic pharmaceuticals. Demand for Halal pharmaceutical, generic medical, wellness and healthcare products are estimated to be about USD555 billion in Muslim-majority countries.

Nutraceuticals usually refers to healthcare products formulated in pharmaceutical dosage forms like capsules or tablets and carry a limited health claim. They are produced under GMP conditions and are currently used as evidence based healthcare products providing protection against chronic disease conditions or having physiological benefits. Examples are flavonoid antioxidants from various herbs (*misai kucing*, *pegaga*), beta-carotene from palm oil, and anthocyanins from berries. Many botanical and herbal extracts such as *lingzhi*, *tongkat ali*, *kunyit* have been developed as nutraceuticals. Numerous claims on nutraceuticals are being researched and many citations are available via PubMed. Examples of claims made are, sinensetin flavonoids from *misai kucing* as an antioxidant, soluble dietary fiber products such as psyllium seed husk for reducing hypercholesterolemia, broccoli (sulforaphane) as a cancer preventative and soy isoflavonoids for arterial health.

The food and the pharmaceutical industries often add nutraceuticals as nutrient premixes or nutrient compositions in their products. The Malaysian natural products industry was worth about RM 8 billion in 2005, consisting of Flavours or Fragrances at RM 2.5 billion, Pharmaceuticals or Nutraceuticals at RM 1.4 billion and Herbal Remedies at RM 3.3 billion. The market is expected to reach RM 10 billion by 2010 (Source MARDI/MHC). In view of the huge economic value and potential of nutraceuticals, certain value added feature must be looked into to ensure that unique niches areas and capabilities are in place for Malaysia to benefit greatly in this competitive area.

A holistic approach to personal health and healthcare is a core tenant of Islam, but Muslims have struggled to adopt a Halal-centric approach to preventative as well as reactive medicine due to the lack of an all-encompassing Halal ecosystem. This has contributed to major healthcare challenges in much of the Muslim world, evidenced in the growing phenomena of inoculation refusals over concerns about the Halal status of vaccines. At the preventative stage, Saudi Arabia's AJ Pharma has launched a polio vaccine that is animal-

component free, and is to launch an inactivated polio vaccine in 2019. Such vaccines should help to counter refusals by Muslim and non-Muslim consumers that are concerned about the health risks of inoculations. Also, at one end of the preventative spectrum is the growing range of Halal nutraceuticals, vitamins and supplements on the market, while key players are focusing on formulations backed by science to enhance efficacy and consumer trust.

Such developments can be coupled with the newly conceived concept of Halalopathy which is the Islamic version of homeopathy. Halalopathy combines religion and modern science, with a core emphasis on the purity of Halal and tayyib, all of the ingredients used in medicine and food to enhance a patient's recovery in line with their beliefs. Malaysia's Halal Industry Development Corporation (HDC) currently compiling the first Halal pharmacopoeia, while JAKIM is to introduce Halal certification for medical devices, including liquids for dialysis machines. The foundations for Halal pharmaceuticals are becoming more solid, and will be strengthened by OIC countries increasing local pharmaceutical production, mainly the UAE, Saudi Arabia and Iran, through numerous joint ventures have been inked over the past year.

The UAE inked a memorandum of understanding with Jafza, a DP World company, to attract more than 75 major pharmaceutical firms by 2021 and doubling the number of manufacturing facilities from 17 to 34. The agreement aims to attract investments of up to USD544 million a year. Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 is encouraging the development of private-public partnerships to develop the localisation of the pharmaceutical industry to ensure adequate supplies. The Iranian government aims to boost the ratio of domestically produced biopharmaceuticals to 75% within five years. The USD1.93 billion market is forecast to grow to USD3.59 billion by 2025. Pharmaniaga Bhd is to build Malaysia's second Halal vaccine plant, following Saudi Arabia-based AJ Pharma's investment in a Halal vaccine facility in the Southeast Asian region. A feasibility study for a plant in northern Malaysia is being carried out

in conjunction with Technology Depository Agency Bhd (TDA) and New Delhi-based Hilleman Laboratories, with production to start by 2020 until 2022.

3.3 COSMETICS

Growth in the Halal cosmetics market is mirrored by a growth in consumer knowledge about the ingredients used and product awareness, fuelled by social networks. The State of the Global Islamic Economy (SGIE) 2018/2019 estimates that Muslim spend on cosmetics was valued at USD 61 billion in 2017, and growing at 6.9% forecast to reach USD 90 billion by 2023. Based on total Muslim cosmetics expenditure, the top 5 countries are India, Indonesia, Russia, Turkey, and Malaysia. The emerging Halal cosmetic and personal care market is seen by analysts as next in line for growth after the lucrative Halal food sector. In the scope of Halal cosmetics, the concept covers critical aspects of production such as Halal ingredients and usage of permissible substances which must be manufactured, stored, packaged and delivered in conformity with Syariah requirements.

The main driver for this huge demand in Halal cosmetics and beauty products stems from the demographic of young, religiously conscious, and dynamic professional Muslim population. The popularity of Halal cosmetics among millennial in Northern America, Europe, the Middle East and East Asia has prompted more market entrants and the expansion of established players seeking global market share. Interestingly, Halal cosmetics has also gained momentum amongst modern consumers who are eco-ethical conscious and are willing to pay a premium for natural, organic and plant-based cosmetics products to suit their modern lifestyle. However, the domination of this sector by small and medium-sized enterprises, does face challenges, notably from multinationals with Halal lines in Muslim-majority countries that have large marketing budgets and strong retail presence.

New Halal cosmetics companies continue to be launched, primarily startups clustered around the Halal hubs of North America, the UK, Malaysia and South Korea. For example, Halal-certified beard oils are on the rise, with the UK's Akhi Beards joining other startups like Double Sunnah and Elegance catering to Muslim men. Besides, multinational companies continue to be reticent to enter the segment, with launches focused on Muslim-majority countries. Malaysia's Duck Group launched a Halal cosmetics range, including lipsticks, eye shadow, and creams. South Korea's Beauarti, a Halal cosmetics brand manufactured by C&B Global, has expanded its presence in Malaysia, a core market. The firm said that since launching in 2017, it has over 1,000 customers a month. Unilever Indonesia launched the Pureline Hijab Fresh moisturizer line. Following its Sunsilk Hijab Recharge shampoo line in 2016, Unilever Indonesia is expanding its products portfolio catering to Muslim women, with an eye on exports.

3.4 OTHERS (TOURISM AND LOGISTICS)

Halal tourism or Muslim-friendly tourism (MFT) has recently gained popularity, and is now fast becoming a new phenomenon in the general tourism industry. It refers to tourism products that provide hospitality services in accordance with Islamic beliefs and practices. The State of the Global Islamic Economy (SGIE) 2018/2019 estimates that Muslim spend on travel was valued at USD 177 billion in 2017, and growing at 7.6% forecast to reach USD 274 billion by 2023. The top 5 world leading Islamic economy ecosystem for Halal travel based on Global Islamic Economy (GIE) Indicator are UAE, Malaysia, Turkey, Indonesia and Maldives. Based on total Muslim travel expenditure, the top 5 countries are Saudi Arabia, UAE, Qatar, Kuwait and Indonesia.

Halal tourism is becoming increasingly digitized with ventures into AI and virtual reality. The digitization of travel is expanding to sub-sectors that were previously bureaucratic, including the hajj and Umrah sectors. For instance, Safa Software Company launched an Umrah and hajj booking portal as well as a hajj and Umrah visa processing portal. Saudi Arabia is launching smart buses for the 2018 Hajj season. Seventeen thousand GPS powered tablets will be provided to the buses, which will allow the buses to be tracked electronically and allow for redirecting bus routes. Moreover, the Halal travel industry is starting to experiment with AI and Virtual Reality such as Have Halal Will Travel launched a chat bot named Sofia which provides customized recommendations based on machine learning.

Driverless and high-speed transportation, part of the future of transport, are also already being launched in the GCC, which will naturally enhance the experience in Halal travel. Dubai's Roads and Transport Authority (RTA) launched the Dubai World Challenge for Self-Driving Transport, as part of its plan to transform 25% of transportation trips in the city into driverless trips by 2030. A high-speed electric train will start running between Makkah and Madinah by September 2018 and is scheduled to become fully operational by early 2019. Lastly, oil-rich GCC countries are taking into account to increase tourism revenue as a measure to diversify their revenue sources and decrease their dependence on oil. Saudi Tourism Commission launched 'Destination for Muslims' Initiative which targets Umrah visitors, Muslim business people, and Muslim transit passenger, to whom it will offer tourism products, through investment of USD64 billion on entertainment infrastructure in the next 10 years such as first cinemas in 2018 and first amusement park in 2022.

Traditionally, logistics emerged from the term physical distribution (Ballou, 2007), and according to Chen and Paulraj (2007) and Christopher (2011), logistics is the process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficient flow and storage of goods (materials, parts and finished inventory), services and related information from the origin to the point of

consumption, by ensuring cost-efficient orders are met. In addition, Lambert et al. (1998) states that the objective of logistics management is to achieve customer satisfaction by ensuring that products or services are made available at the right time, in the right quantity, with the right description and in good condition. Therefore, logistics management involves a series of activities namely transportation, storage and warehousing, inventory management, material management, product scheduling, customer service and so forth. Hence, to achieve total Halal logistics, these elements must also be Halal, and because of integrity issues and the complex nature of logistics and supply chain, the need for Halal logistics is ever more important.

Presently, Muslims are more aware of their food consumption (Bonne et al., 2007; Bonne & Verbeke, 2008), and the need for Halal-certified products and services does not only matter during point of purchase or consumption, but the whole supply chain, from upstream to downstream (Tieman, 2011). Ideally, Tieman (2013) defined Halal logistics as the process of managing the procurement, movement, storage and handling of materials, parts, livestock, semi-finished or finished inventory both food and non-food, and related information and documentation flows through the organization and the supply chain in compliance with the general principles of Shariah. From this definition, it indicates that the distribution of Halal products and services depends on Halal logistics functions. This can be explained by Smith (2007) that the growth of Halal industry depends on the success of Halal logistics, and it is the key in facilitating the manufacturing and distribution of Halal products and services.

According to Tieman et al. (2012) and Tieman (2013), transportation, warehousing and terminal operation are critical areas for Halal logistics. This can be justified by Jaafar et al., (2011) and Talib et al. (2013) that many logistics service providers (LSP) are investing in Halal dedicated facilities into their operation, such as warehousing and transportation fleet specialized for Halal products storage and distribution. Furthermore, to conform to strict Halal requirements and fulfil customers' demand, LSP have gone extra miles to ensure Halal logistics

success. Value-added services such as samak/sertu (ritual cleansing) or steam cleaning for containers, temperature-controlled warehouses, dedicated transport carriers, Halal-only tools and equipment and complete segregation during distribution and storage are some notable examples (Jaafar et al., 2011; Kamaruddin et al., 2012; Tieman et al., 2012; Tieman, 2013).

4.0 CHALLENGES IN HALAL INDUSTRY.

The first challenge is the confusion surrounding Halal standards, primarily because they are being produced by so many different government-linked organizations; private organizations and independent Halal certification bodies (HCB's); national standards bodies, regional bodies such as ASEAN, GSO and the EU; and international bodies such as the SMIC or OIC initiative. The challenge for manufacturers is to determine which standard will actually provide market access, and in too many cases multiple certificates are necessary for exporters (Thomson Reuters and Dinar Standard, 2016). Halal certification is a necessary operational step to addressing Muslim needs, but the lack of global alignment on certification increases costs and can destroy value. The studies conduct by Talib et al., 2013 stated that ineffective system of halal will directly result in increasing the cost for implementation. Halal falls below global best practices due to a lack of commonly accepted standards among certification bodies globally, oftentimes resulting in duplicate certification costs and added complexity. Besides, Malaysian Halal certification need to be coherent to other qualifications like Malaysian Standard MS1500 and general guidelines on the production, preparation, handling and storage of Halal foods which comply to the most widely recognized and established standard; GMP and GHP to further heightened its calibre.

Secondly, the absence of any viable international schemes to accredit Halal certification bodies (HCBs) has long been a problem for the Halal industry (Hussein Elastrag, 2016). The majority of Halal food is being produced in Non-Muslim majority countries, and is certified by

independent HCB's that operate with little regulatory oversight. There are over 300 officially recognized certifiers globally, but there remains limited oversight by impartial accreditation bodies, leaving substantial room for misrepresentation. Current accreditation initiatives, such as being developed by SMIIC, GSO and ESMA are all moves in the right direction, more coordination between the accreditation bodies is needed to avoid unnecessary duplication or competition. The third challenge is the difficulty to obtain shariah-compliance funding (Sohail et al, 2006). Companies wishing to scale or to vertically integrate their supply chain face challenges in obtaining shariah-compliance funding. The slow financing approval process which particularly by the government linked financial institutions has diminished the spirit of small and medium enterprise (SMEs) to expand their production capacity to meet export demand.

Another challenges for manufacturer is the role to meet Halal requirement itself. It is crucial for government to monitor and supervise all manufacturers especially in food field. The main idea is to ensure manufactured products should be free from contamination and should not contain any haram ingredients during its preparation, production and storage (Talib et al., 2013). The total quality management practice needs to be applied for the purpose of marketing Halal products where the food manufacturer should not only focus on methods for Halal certification. Therefore, quality assurance and wholesomeness could increase the demand for such products. The stiff regional competition such as Thailand, Indonesia, Brunei and other Asian countries as these countries aiming to be the global Halal players is also one of challenges that focusing on small and medium enterprise (SME). For instance, non-Muslim countries such as Thailand, Brazil, Argentina, Australia and New Zealand are already actively producing Halal certified meat to cater to the increasing needs of the Muslim consumers around the world. Thus, the local SMEs will need guidance and assistance especially to explore new export markets.

Furthermore, there seem to be lack of supply for Halal raw materials especially meat products. This is where there is high percentage, about 70% of raw materials for food processing being imported. The supply of raw material also becomes one of the main issues in Malaysia (Sazelin Arif, 2008). The unsteady regulatory and agricultural production environment would affect the supply of raw materials. It may cause the Halal food industry fails to meet the expectation and demands of consumers. Recognizing this need, small entrepreneurs should take advantage of business opportunities to reap the benefits of increasing profits for halal industry. As to ensure the compliance of these raw materials with Malaysian Halal standard, suppliers should always be in contact with the Malaysia's certification body, JAKIM.

In addition, the speed of issuing Halal logo is another challenges faced by JAKIM. This could be due to JAKIM not having a fully-fledged research and development unit to test, analyze and doing on-site inspection (Zulkifli Hassan, 2007). It is now being done by a third party that enables the Halal application at the appointed time. The term traceability is highly related to the Halal concept. Traceability promotes transparency as well as ensures information is accessible along the supply chain. For instance, several enforcement programs that conducted by the Malaysian authorities after the enactment of the Trade Description Act (TDA) 2011, many food manufacturers and food premises were caught as using unrecognized Halal certificates at their premises or on their product's packaging.

For pharmaceutical or nutraceutical, cosmetics and health products, the main challenge is lack of global alignment on certification that will increase costs and can destroy value. Vaccination refusal is a global phenomenon and is on the rise in Muslim-majority countries, posing the threat of epidemics. This is partly due to the perceived prevalence of porcine gelatin in vaccines, with only two major companies manufacturing Halal or animal-component free vaccines, Novartis and AJ Pharma. There's been a notable rise in vaccination refusal in certain

Muslim-majority countries, such as Malaysia, due to doubts about Halal compliance. An estimated 19.9 million infants worldwide were not immunized in 2017, with a high percentage in Muslim-majority countries. If animal-component free vaccines are successfully marketed to Muslim and non-Muslim consumers alike, the sector could be worth USD50 billion by 2020. A challenge is the lack of government support and qualified Halal certifiers (Zhari, 2007). AJ Pharma has launched a polio vaccine that is animal-component free, and is to launch an inactivated polio vaccine in 2019. However, it has not been able to get Halal certification due to the limited of Halal standards.

Insufficient Muslim auditors who are trained in Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) guidelines is also one of the challenges (Talib et al, 2013). The use of GMP guidelines which important for maintaining quality, is correspond with a country's legislation for pharmaceutical, cosmetics and personal care products have been designed to improve product quality and traceability to protect human life and help ensure that products are pure and healthy (tayyib). It is not just a case of detecting non-Halal ingredients but also the unethical masbooh ingredients (best to avoid) because of damaging effects from them absorbed through the skin or internally with medication. Ensuring that Halal auditors and technical experts have this training is essential for the growth of Halal certified pharmaceuticals and cosmetics.

For tourism sector, the challenges that commonly be face is when accommodate both Muslims and non-Muslims at the same destination. Business Emirates, 2009 on their report state that normally 4 stars hotels and above will provide an exclusive bar for the guest and this definitely against the shariah compliant requirement. This is also especially relevant to beach destinations, where Muslims want to avoid gazing at bikini-clad Westerners, while some non-Muslims prefer to party freely without being followed by watchful eyes. One approach to avoid this is designating separate areas for Muslims and others for non-Muslims but an indirect impact will occur where certainly it will reduce the number of tourists who want to stay at the

hotel (Mohd Rizal Razalli et al., 2012). The Indonesian island, Lombok does precisely on that. In order to avoid putting off non-Muslim visitors to Lombok, as well as avoid offending Muslim tourists by the skimpy outfits worn by sunbathers, the local government has identified areas that are suited to Muslim guests, where Western tourists need to cover up, whereas, party hotspots in the area, such as the tiny Gili Trawangan island off the West coast of Lombok remain unaffected.

Other than that, marketing to Muslim travellers without alienating non-Muslims is also crucial challenges to all hotelier. Hotels and destinations that cater to Muslim tourists certainly do not want to attract the Muslim traveller segment at the expense of other markets, and therefore one dilemma is what their marketing strategy should be. One approach is to market themselves as a family-friendly hotel/destination without using the terms “Muslim” or “Halal” (Henderson JC, 2010). For instance, Al Jawhara, a Dubai-based hotel group through their ads has promotes its “unique family oriented hospitality”, despite the fact that the hotel clearly caters to Muslim needs. Another hotel group that successfully accommodates Muslim needs while being inclusive and not branding itself as a Halal hotel is Shaza Hotels. The luxury hotel operator focuses on authentic Arabian hospitality while being values-driven, and therefore appeals to both Muslims and non-Muslims alike. Another way to avoid the dilemma of marketing to Muslims while non-alienating others, is to market to the Muslim audience through targeted marketing channels, such as Muslim media, local publications in Muslim majority countries, as well as targeted ad campaigns.

4.1 OTHER CHALLENGES IN HALAL INDUSTRY

Modest fashion is growing fast as an industry, but with it, there is increasing commoditization, with the consumer ultimately losing out. There has been a remarkable growth of independent brands, but noticeably, the well-capitalized leaders in the apparel industry are also entering the industry, with limited engagement with the Muslim consumer base. The funding received by the independent, Muslim-native brands, is exciting, but larger multinationals are driving commoditization. The independent brands have shown an astute customer engagement strategy, with encouraging growth in the leading independent brands, noticeably Khaadi and the Aidijuma group, as well as the funding received in the past year by the Modist. However, competition in the industry is very intense, with the largest multinationals much better capitalized. Moreover, the lack of astuteness of brands across fashion and beauty in understanding consumer needs is evident with the misstep, which would naturally extend to users of Modest Fashion that was taken by MAC Cosmetics in creating a video on how to apply makeup for Suhoor for UAE-based Muslims, which was criticized by a broader global audience.

Meanwhile, Halal media struggles to secure funding despite its strong fundamentals. With Muslims spending USD209 billion on media and recreation globally, and despite strong potential to create a multi-billion-dollar enterprise that complements offline Islamic education, the lack of investment is worrying. Halal media could become a viable force for good, changing Muslim narratives especially in the west, but more funding is needed. There is much to learn from other Abrahamic religions — Christian filmmakers set up their own studios and produced a number of successful films such as ‘God’s Not Dead (2014)’ that gross tens of millions of dollars. The ecosystem of creative Islamic offerings is improving — across movies, children, game shows, and documentaries — going beyond traditional religious lectures. However, a very limited number have taken place, despite previous fund announcements, such

as Abwab Capital in 2014/15. Alchemiya’s struggle to raise USD1 million in crowd funding further highlights a challenge.

5.0 EMERGING OPPORTUNITIES IN HALAL INDUSTRY.

The halal industry has emerged as a new evolution sector in the global economy and is creating a strong presence in developed countries. Challenges lies in the industry are actually a gap and opportunities to tap by the industry players. Therefore, Islamic economy companies play an important role in addressing Muslim consumer needs and play a critical role in driving economic growth and activity. The Indicator measures the strength of the Islamic economy for 73 countries, across supply and demand drivers, governance, awareness and social considerations. Therefore, here are the main components of growth’s factors in Halal industry:

Figure 4: Component of Opportunities in Halal Industry

5.1 SIZEABLE AND GROWING MUSLIM POPULATION

Among the main aspects for the robust growth of the Islamic Economy sectors is the fast growing, young, and increasing number of Muslim population worldwide. According to Pew Research projections on the Future of World Religion (2015), stated that by 2050 there will be 2.8 billion Muslims (30% of the population) worldwide.

Projected Annual Growth Rate of Country Populations, 2010-2050

Figure 5: The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections, 2010-2050.

5.2 GROWING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF HALAL BUSINESS.

The Islamic Economy continues to evolve, driven by young Muslims asserting their values and requiring companies to provide products and services that meet their faith-based needs. Besides that, participation from non-Muslim in also contribute to the growth of Islamic economy globally. Looking at the potential in terms of economy benefits and changing lifestyle for healthy and good virtue in this industry has attract the attention of non-Muslim as well.

Figure 6: Halal Industry Development (2016).

5.5 ISLAMIC VALUES INCREASINGLY DRIVING LIFESTYLE AND BUSINESS PRACTICES.

Islam as a 'way of life' for many Muslims continues to guide all aspects of their lives, including their consumption behavior. Indeed, the practice and adherence to Islam varies greatly among Muslims based on their age group, geographic region/ country, cultural influences and other factors.

According to a Pew Global Attitudes survey (2015), selected 42 countries, 83% of respondents from Islamic countries considered "religion as very important in their lives."

Anecdotally, a growing prominence in the media of Muslim women wearing hijab as Olympic athletes and professionals are asserting their rights through Modest Fashion clothing. Many of these values do have a universal appeal and thus many products and services do not have to be exclusively positioned for Muslims.

6.0 CONCLUSION

The Halal industry is progressively growing and attained attention among industry players globally. The comprehensiveness of the industry which integrated into all sectors, makes it an attractive niche for business to invest in as the opportunities are boundless. Moving forward, the Halal industry is expected to remain on this path as it gathers more attention and exposure worldwide.

There are substantial opportunities in adjacent sectors including Healthcare and Education, estimated at \$436 billion and \$402 billion in 2015 respectively, to address the needs of Muslims with tailored offerings, with convergence opportunities in particular in Islamic Economy education and medical tourism.

By classification, food & beverage holds the biggest share in the halal industry. In the Global Islamic Economic Report 2017-2018 stated that, the halal F&B consumption is valued at USD1.24 trillion. The Halal pharmaceuticals and cosmetics sector is said to be growing with the innovation of Halal nail polish and makeup. Muslims spend on pharmaceuticals is forecast to reach USD132 billion by 2022. Pharmaniaga, a Malaysian pharmaceutical company is set to invest RM100 million to develop halal and cost-effective vaccines for the public.

For current and prospective Halal industry players, government agencies and investment firms, the time is prepared to participate in the Islamic Economy across all key pillars, and to generate substantial returns. The involvement of governments and private sectors contribute to the sustainability of the Halal ecosystem through certification by religious authorities as well as implementation of policies is vital to boost the halal industry. Religious authorities of several countries are also working together towards establishing a global Halal standard, which would ensure an even more sustainable industry going forward.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, K. A. (2008). Financing Halal Business: Islamic solutions for Muslim entrepreneurs in Malaysia. *International Conference on Entrepreneurship*.
- Abdalhamid Evans. (2011). "Towards a Halal Economy: The Power of Values in Global Markets". *The Halal Journal*, vol 12. Business Emirates 8 March 2009, <http://www.business24-7.ae>, accessed 27 February 2019.
- Ballou, (2007) The Evolution and Future of Logistics and Supply Chain Management, *European Business Review*, Vol. 19 Issue: 4, pp.332-348.
- Bohari, A.M., Cheng, W.H. and Fuad, N. (2013), "An analysis on the competitiveness of Halal food industry in Malaysia: an approach of SWOT and ICT strategy", *Malaysia Journal of Society and Space*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 1-9.

- Bonne, K. and Verbeke, W. 2007. Muslim Consumer's Attitude towards Meat Consumption in Belgium: Insights From A Means-End Chain Approach. *Anthropology of Food* 5: 1-24.
- Bonne, K. and Verbeke, W. (2008), Muslim Consumer Trust In Halal Meat Status And Control In Belgium, *Meat Science*, Vol. 79 No. 1, pp. 113-123.
- Christopher, M. (2011). *Logistics & Supply Chain Management*. Dorchester, UK: Financial Times/Prentice Hall.
- COMCEC. 2016. Muslim Friendly Tourism: Understanding the Demand and Supply Sides In the OIC Member Countries.
- Fleishman-Hillard Majlis. (2012). "The Next billion: The Market Opportunity of the Muslim World". The World Halal Summit, Kuala Lumpur 4-5 April.
- From niche to mainstream: Halal Goes Global. 2015. International Trade Centre.
- Halal Journal (2008). Halal Food Market A Multi-Billion Dollar Global Opportunity, *Halal Journal*.
- Halal Industry Development Corporation (HDC) 2012. Halal Parks in Malaysia. Retrieved: Retrieved from www.hdcglobal.com.
- Halal Industry Development Corporation. (2016) Halal Industry the New Potential Market. volume 1.
- Humayon Dar, Nursofiza Azmi, Rizwan Rahman and Rizwan Malik. 2013. Chapter 13-18 Global Islamic Financial Report 2013. Edbiz Consulting Limited.
- Hussein Elasrag. 2016. Halal Industry: Key Challenges and Opportunities. *Munich Personal RePEc Archiv (MPRA)*.
- Henderson, J.C., Managing tourism and Islam in Peninsular Malaysia. *Tourism Management*, 2010. 34: p. 447-456.
- Ismail, Z. and Ehsan, A.H. (2008), "Halal Nutraceutical Market: issues and challenges", in *AFBE 2008 Conference*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, pp. 573-597.

- Ishak, F. I., & Man, Y. C. (2011). Halal Economy: Proof from Al-Quran and As-Sunnah and Demands to Utilize It in Parallel. *International Islamic Banking, Finance and Investment Conference*.
- IslamOnline.net (2005). Malaysian "Halal Journal" hits UK, UAE Markets. Retrieved from <http://www.islamonline.net/English/News/2005-02/21/article04.shtml>.
- IslamOnline.net (2006). Malaysian halal food industry a role model. Retrieved from <http://www.IslamOnline.net>.
- IFSB. (2009). Guiding Principles On Shari`Ah Governance Systems For Institutions Offering Islamic Financial Services. Kuala Lumpur: Islamic Financial Services Board.
- Jaafar, H. S., Endut, I. R., Faisol, N., & Omar, E. N. (2011). Innovation in logistics services-halal logistics. *In the 16th International Symposium on Logistics (ISL)* (pp. 844-851).
- Kim, H. Y. and Chung, J. E. (2011). Consumer purchase intention for organic personal care products. *Journal of consumer Marketing*, 28(1), 40-47. Retrieved from Emerald Group Publishing Ltd.
- Kamaruddin, R. , Iberahim, H. and Shabudin, A. (2012), "Willingness to pay for Halal logistics: the lifestyle choice". *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 50, pp. 722-729.
- Lada S, Tanakinjal HG, Amin H. (2010). Predicting intention to choose halal products using theory of reasoned action. *International journal Islamic Middle East Finance Management*, 2(1): 66-76.
- Lambert, D.M., Stock, J.R. and Ellram, L.M. (1998), *Fundamentals of Logistics Management*, McGraw Hill, Singapore.
- Mahathir M. (April 2010). Halal cosmetic to spur global halal industry. *SME New*, 25-26.

- Malaysia International Islamic Financial Centre. (MIFC). (2014). Shariah screening methodology: Adopting a two-tier quantitative approach. Retrieved from <http://www.mifc.com>.
- Mohd Aliff Abdul Majid, Izhar Hafifi Zainal Abidin, Hayati Adilin Mohd Abd Majid & Chemah Tamby Chik. (2015). Issues of Halal Food Implementation in Malaysia. *Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences* 5(6S) 50-56, 2015.
- Mukhtar & Butt, (2012) Intention to choose Halal products: The Role Of Religiosity, *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, Vol. 3 Issue: 2, pp.108-120.
- Norafni Farlina Rahim, Z. S. (2016). Awareness and Perception of Muslim Consumers on Non-Food Halal Product. *Journal of Social and Development Sciences*, 478-487
- Noriah Ramli, Naemah Amin , Majdah Zawawi & Norazlina Abdul Aziz. (2018). Healthcare Services: Halal Pharmaceutical In Malaysia, Issues And Challenges. *Pew Research Center*. (2015). Global Attitudes Spring survey.
- Pew Research Center. (2015). The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections, 2010-2050.
- Paulraj, A., & Chen, I. J. (2007). Environmental uncertainty and strategic supply management: A resource dependence perspective and performance implications. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 43(3), 29–42.
- Razalli, M.R. et al. (2012), Developing a Model for Islamic Hotels: Evaluating Opportunities and Challenges, Universiti Utara Malaysia.
- Sazelin Arif (2008). Keupayaan Pasaran Dalam Kalangan Pengusaha Kecil Makanan Halal di Melaka Tengah: Satu Kajian Awal.
- SME Annual Report 2006 (2007). Potential growth areas for SMEs. National SME Development Council, Kuala Lumpur.
- State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2016/17. 2016. Thomson Reuters.

- State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2018/19. 2018. Thomson Reuters.
- Siddiqui, K. (2013), "An exploratory study for measuring consumers awareness and perceptions towards Halal food in Pakistan", *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 639-652.
- Smith, C. C. (2007). Halal Logistics a Fast-growing Market. Bangkok Post. Retrieved from <http://halalrc.org/images/ResearchMaterial/Literature/Halallogisticsafastgrowingmark> et.
- Sohail, M.S., Bhatnagar, R. and Sohal, A.S. (2006), "A comparative study on the use of third party logistics services by Singaporean and Malaysian firms", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, Vol. 36 No. 9, pp. 690-701.
- Talib, A. N. A., & Razak, I. S. A. (2013). Cultivating export market oriented behavior in halal marketing: Addressing the issues and challenges in going global. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 4(2), 187-197.
- Tieman, M. (2011), "The application of Halal in supply chain management: in-depth interviews", *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 186-195.
- Tieman, M. (2010). Halal Logistics. Retrieved from <http://www.logasiamag.com/article/halallogistics>
- Tieman, M. (2013), "Establishing the principles in Halal logistics", *Journal of Emerging Economies and Islamic Research*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 1-13.
- Thomson Reuters and Dinar Standard (2016). "State of the Global Islamic Economy 2015/16 Report." Thomson Reuters and Dinar Standard, New York City.
- Trade Descriptions Act (Definition of Halal) Order 2011.
- Yuhanis, A. A., & Chok, N. V. (2012). The role of Halal awareness and Halal certification in influencing non-muslims' purchase intention. *Prosiding in 3rd International conference on Business and Economic Research*.

Zulkifli Hasan (2007). Undang-Undang Produk Halal di Malaysia: Isu Penguatkuasaan dan Pendakwaan.

Zhari I. (2007), Issues and Challenges in Halal Pharmaceuticals, presented at the *International Conference on Research Advances in Halal Science, HDC, Kuala Lumpur, November 2007*.